

METHODOLOGY OF MUSIC TEACHING IN FOREIGN COUNTRIES

Joraeva Sanobarkhon Azamjonovna

Master's student of direction: "Music education and art", Faculty of Pedagogy, Namangan state pedagogical institute

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10143304>

Abstract. *The methodology of teaching music in foreign countries is somewhat different from ours. The spiritual food that you get from this musical knowledge serves as an important factor in the upbringing of the child and his future role.*

Keywords: *electronic organ, sudoku system, enlightenment, visual imagination, creativity.*

Music education of any country serves the social system of the people from an ideological and political point of view. Therefore, music education in independent countries serves for religion and in foreign countries for bourgeois democracy. The methodology of educational music education of each nation is based on the didactic laws of pedagogy and the language and cultural traditions of the national music culture of this nation. At the same time, the structural system of music education (system) and scientific-methodical achievements have a positive effect on the educational culture of other nations.

A uniform curriculum and program is not followed in foreign countries. Along with public schools, there are private colleges and higher educational institutions, which give students wide creative freedom in aesthetic education. The teacher can introduce adaptations to the program depending on the possibilities of his situation and the level of knowledge of the students, and in the process of education, the students develop the skills of creative attitude to life and personal attitude to it through art. Highly developed technical means are widely used in music. Pupils play electronic organs and sing, perform various activities (speech movements, accompanying each other). It mainly consists in realizing the students' creative abilities. In particular, there is no single state program in the USA. Music education is defined as "aesthetics". In it, music, fine art and cocktail are connected with each other. Along with public schools, there are also religious and private secular schools. Therefore, in every school, public schools, private and religious schools, the educational activities are not the same. In addition to the lessons, there is a symphony orchestra in the same school with members of each student's music clubs (choir, orchestra, dance).

Even in Japan, a uniform curriculum and program is not followed. A unique system of music education has been created in Japan. They provide aesthetic education from kindergarten to higher education. Aesthetic education is an integrated science, in which music, visual arts and cocktails are integrated. It is done in several stages.

- a) in kindergarten up to 1-5 years old
- b) Incomplete high school for 6-14 years
- c) 15-18-year-old secondary school
- g) 18-23 years old higher education school

The "Sundo'ku" system is popular in kindergarten¹ in the system, it is carried out by teaching the mother tongue and listening to music. Melodies also play a role in children's musical instruments. The children's mother also participates in the training process. He is aware of the content and purpose of the training and is engaged in his voice in the family. It is not necessary for mothers to have musical knowledge at Sundoku's events. They discuss the works listened to on gramophone, television, and concerts in the family. The cooperation of kindergarten and family also plays a role in this. As a result, 5-6-year-old children can play Beethoven sonatas. As you move to higher classes, "aesthetic education becomes more complicated, like a subject. Painting, sculpture, folk art are taught in classes and critics of the art of music are enough.

According to the Law of Uzbekistan "On Education" 9-year general secondary education was introduced. The concept of education in music was developed taking into account the regional characteristics. On November 25, 1992, in the "Enlightenment" newspaper, in the project of the concept of music education, the national and scientific foundations, content, structure of music education, its classification, modern requirements for a music teacher and its scientific methodical supply was explained². Realizing our identity today has the opportunity to create the perspective of our destiny and our children, and in the schools of restoring the uniqueness of our national culture in independent Uzbekistan, it is considered a good knowledge of our history to educate young people artistically and to fully perceive our present day. Because each of them is made through historical connection. The introduction of state educational standards in musical education, as well as in all subjects, allows full use of national musical heritage. These are reflected in the creative activities of singers and musicians in folk songs, status, "shashmakom", epics, and today's modern musical activities.

Such possibilities of musical art will serve as a unique resource for educating the new generation. From music education, educational content based on state educational standards ensures the development of students' musical knowledge and experiences, such as observation, memory comparison, visual imagination, creativity, independence, initiative, artistic and musical taste. Therefore, musical culture lessons are important in educating the young generation.

Musical culture lessons have a positive effect on the moral and aesthetic education of students. It develops their sense of beauty, instills love and interest in the art of music, teaches them to love the Motherland, respect each other, elders, work, love nature, and in life helps to find one's place. In this case, the goal of music education is to make students learn an art with all its sophistication, to perceive music, to sing and dance individually and as a team, and to form creative skills. It is also a necessary condition for developing students' talents. -creating conditions and satisfying their artistic needs is the task of music education. Today's music education shows that music lessons and music education outside the classroom are of great importance to our national musical heritage. In order to implement music lessons in life, based on the standard of general secondary schools, the main essence of the new program is first of all, the topics of the lesson are taken from the main topics determined every quarter. Music is used to make the lesson interesting, all musical activities (listening to music in a choir) are an integral part of the lesson and are logically connected. The lesson is the most convenient and effective form of education. Political, economic, and social educational changes in various aspects of our society place new modern demands on the content and methodology of music lessons along with all subjects:

¹ "Sundo'ku" o'yin metodi Yaponiya davlatida bolalar bog'chasida olib boriladi.

² Mustaqilligimiz tomonidan chiqarilgan "Marifat" ro'znomasi 1992 yil 25-noyabrsagi soni

1. Knowing the educational-didactic, educational and developmental goals in the lesson and their implementation.
2. Using active methods and methods of education in the lesson.
3. In the course of the lesson, it is appropriate to use the traditions of folk pedagogy, the psychology of world pedagogy, the teachings of our great ancestors, our narrations, and our wise hadiths.

It is known that the research conducted in recent years by experienced methodologists, scientists and practicing students in the field of learning process analysis shows that the improvement of lesson efficiency depends on pedagogical and didactic conditions. The most important conditions are as follows: Textbooks, manuals, program recommendations, use of didactic visual aids and technical tools, positive psychological atmosphere in the classroom, good relationship between teachers and students. If the subject of the lesson is followed by the pedagogical conditions, the lesson can be qualitatively and effectively organized if it is properly organized. The methodist-teacher should show the right way to the trainees by providing methodical support and giving advices, distinguishing their achievements. The main goal and the listeners are to identify the abilities and achievements of our youth and form and reveal them in the right way. In this regard, our country's first president I.A.Karimov said, "We should all understand that the situation in other areas of our life - the effectiveness of our ongoing reforms, first of all, is the revival of the people's spirituality, the wide study of our rich historical heritage, the formation of our traditions, culture and art, science and education. is inextricably linked with the development of³ - with his words, he is calling to strive for the peak of spirituality.

In conclusion, teachers use many methods and methods to teach students the art of music in this way. Such lesson processes help students to become more advanced, through them, they promote the art of music among young people and introduce our art to the world. The art of music in the education of children, the aesthetic knowledge developed in their education, is clearly manifested in the future education of children. It would not be an exaggeration to say that it is one of the important factors in their development into a mature person in the future.

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³ Birinchi prezidentimiz I. A. Karimov so'zlagan nutqlaridan